

Biodegradation of diclofenac in a sequencing batch reactor with aerobic granular sludge

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1. Introduction – Diclofenac (DCF) is as an anti-inflammatory drug regarded as a contaminant of emerging concern due to its extensive use and resistance to removal in wastewater (WW) treatment plants [1]. Therefore, developing efficient DCF removal processes is crucial to successfully mitigate its environmental impact. Aerobic granular sludge (AGS) technology, known for its excellent settling capacity, resilience against perturbations, and nutrient removal efficiency, shows promise in WW treatment [1]. This work aimed to determine AGS potential to biodegrade DCF at environmentally relevant concentrations (20-40 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and assess its effect on AGS microbial community.

2. Experimental – The experimental system consisted of a 2-L anaerobic-aerobic sequencing batch reactor (SBR) inoculated with AGS from a Municipal wastewater treatment plant (Frielas, Loures, Portugal). The SBR was operated in 6h-cycles with 12h of hydraulic retention time, 50% volumetric exchange ratio and no imposed solids retention time, according to Table I. Each cycle had 2h of non-aerated reaction followed by 4h of aeration. Synthetic WW comprising acetate, ammonium, phosphate, and micronutrients in addition to DCF, was prepared with a C:N:P ratio of 100:7:1. Nitrification was inhibited in Period I.

3. Results and Discussion – In general, acetate and ammonium were totally consumed during the SBR cycles. Enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) also occurred, except at the start of Period III, showing that phosphate-accumulating microorganisms were negatively affected by the storage, leading to the disappearance of species such as *Candidatus phosphoribacter*. However, EBPR gradually recovered since day 131. For Periods I and II, DCF removal of approximately 20% was attained, independently of nitrification. The storage period and the increase of DCF concentration in Period III led to lower removal levels (10%) and to DCF accumulation in the SBR up to 40 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ at the onset of the reaction phase (theoretical value of 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Despite 30% DCF removal being attained on day 138 (Image 1), prolonged exposure to DCF concentrations above 30 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ negatively impacted SBR performance, reducing solids content and increasing the flocculent biomass fraction, which was reversed in the absence of DCF (Periods IV and V). Increasing the acetate concentration in the WW (Period VI) while using the same DCF concentration of Period II appeared to not benefit DCF removal, which remained at approximately 20%. DCF adsorption to the biomass was considered irrelevant since its removal was always negligible during the first 2h of non-aerated reaction (Image 1), aerobic biodegradation being the main removal mechanism. The abundance of glycogen-accumulating organisms such as *Propionivibrio dominicans* and *Defluviicoccus spp.* tended to increase in the presence of DCF, and the abundance of some denitrifiers tended to decrease (*Zoogloea caeni*, *Hydrogenophaga caeni*, and *Ca_Compitibacter denitrificans*).

4. Conclusions – DCF removal levels up to 30% were attained in a AGS system when present in synthetic WW in concentrations up to 40 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, the removal being mainly attributed to aerobic biodegradation. However, the prolonged exposure of AGS to DCF concentrations above 30 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ negatively impacted its performance, contributing to structural instability and degranulation, which were reversed in the absence of DCF.

5. References

[1] V. S. Bessa, I.S. Moreira, et al., *Environ. Technol.*, **40** (21), (2022) p.3295.

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Table I. SBR experimental periods.

Experimental period	Operation time (days)	Acetate in WW (mg O ₂ L ⁻¹ as COD)	DCF in WW ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
I	0-80	200	20
II	81-94	200	20
Storage at 4°C for 30 days			
III	95-162	200	40
IV	163-171	200	0
V	172-228	400	0
VI	229-284	400	20

Image 1. Operational cycle in day 138.